
Traditional Christmas Practices in Antequera, Bohol, and Cultural Preservation Mechanisms

Angelica Marie O. Laqui^{1*}, Maria Grethel Joy C. Bajarias², Florymae S. Bonior³, Nicole G. Lagrido⁴, Deseree Jane A. Anunciado⁵, and Fe N. Conui⁶

¹Carmel Academy, Bohol Association of Catholic Schools, Tagbilaran City, Bohol 6300 Philippines

²Commission on Election, Dausi, Bohol 6339, Philippines

³Local Government Unit of Loay, Loay, Bohol 630, Philippines

⁴IBEX Global Solutions, Inc., Tagbilaran City, Bohol 6300, Philippines

⁵College of Technology and Allied Sciences, General Education Department, Bohol Island State University-Balilihan Campus, Balilihan, Bohol 6342, Philippines

⁶College of Education, Holy Name University, Tagbilaran City, Bohol 6300, Philippines

ABSTRACT

This study sought to determine the Christmas practices known in Antequera, Bohol, and the cultural preservation mechanisms they have done on the practices. Many years ago, this town celebrated Christmas, which made it rich in traditional Christmas practices such as *Igue-igue*, *Pastores*, and *Haring Herudes*, which were performed before, during, and after Christmas, respectively. These were combinations of choral and theater-like movements that were performed depending on the desired venue of the host. The locals performed this tradition with a single desire to give praise to the infant Jesus. Researchers used a Descriptive-Qualitative method and Culture Identity Theory to describe and understand the Christmas practices known and observed in Antequera, Bohol. Results showed that the people of Barangay Angilan, Antequera, worked hard to sustain their Christmas practices. It is just that it was not passed down to the younger generation because of several reasons that prevent

them from doing so. The findings of the study would help them ensure sustainability in the implementation of culture and arts programs and activities that strengthen culture preservation, specifically the preservation of the identified Christmas practices. In conclusion, the three Christmas practices are related to each other. People cannot fully understand the significance of the said practices if they are not able to witness them from the start (*Igue-igue*, *Haring Herudes*, and *Pastores*). Old practices do not automatically mean that they are obsolete already. Young folks can still enjoy it as it has values and wisdom that can be imparted to them.

Keywords: *Igue-igue*, *Pastores*, *Haring Herudes*, traditional Christmas practices, cultural preservation mechanisms

INTRODUCTION

The Philippines is known by many as the nation that has the longest celebration of Christmas. With this, most Filipino families start decorating their Christmas trees and putting up their *Belens* on September 1. Different carolers, Christmas-themed performances, and songs are also heard during this season. After months of celebration, it officially ends on the Feast of the Three Kings. For generations, these Spanish-influenced practices were enjoyed, maintained, and passed down.

These Christmas practices were evident in Antequera, Bohol, an inland town that lies in the western part of the island, about 18.5 kilometers from Tagbilaran City. Many years ago, this town celebrated Christmas, which made it rich in traditional Christmas practices. To name a few, the locals had *Igue-Igue*, *Pastores*, and *Haring Herudes*, which were performed before, during, and after Christmas, respectively. These practices were combinations of choral and theater-like movements that were performed depending on the desired venue of the host. The people of Antequera performed this tradition with a single desire to give praise to the infant Jesus.

According to Luspo, in his article entitled 'Daygon' fast disappearing at The Manila Times (December 26, 2015), a

Boholano local cultural historian, each town's history is unique and reflective of Bohol's glorious past and is an important component in designing and planning heritage-based creative hubs. Boholanos have the tradition of preparing something for the birth of Jesus. They decorate their houses with unique Christmas decorations, and they sing old Christmas songs, which are sung from one house to another. It is said to be sung by the old folks when they were still young. However, this old traditional song is seldom practiced because of the rise of modern music. This can be verified in Luspo's statement, as he mentioned that this is due to the emergence and influence of new genres of music, particularly Western music. No one has an interest in learning these Christmas practices because they are afraid of being tagged as outdated.

Another cultural bearer in the name of Simi Guilen, as cited in Bersabal's article (2017), Folk Society's Christmas Musical Tradition Dying in Bohol, said that she is not sure if there would be enough participants that would be gathered because of the lack of interest in today's generation to these practices and this is mainly because of them being too busy with their mobile phones.

This study is anchored on the Cultural Identity Theory that explains the relationship between intercultural competence and cultural identity. This theory deals with how individuals use communicative processes to construct and negotiate their cultural group identities and relationships in particular contexts.

Bohol Arts and Cultural Heritage (BACH) Code seeks to strengthen cultural institutions and regulate even the transfer of cultural properties by requiring appropriate registration. This aims to protect and preserve the province's cultural heritage, properties, and histories to conserve the ethnicity of local communities and the nation as a whole.

The cultural heritage of Antequera is one of the most important assets and elements toward sustainable eco-cultural tourism productivity. Strong support mechanisms are required and are hereby formed by announcing the adherence to both local and international cultural heritage conventions.

Wajdner's (2018) study gives the idea that heritage is a process, and its management should direct people to connect with heritage. It involves helping communities understand themselves and listening to how they identify what is important to them. The government has a primary role in raising the people's awareness of their cultural legacy. The people should be part of every cultural process of development. The people should be involved in the process by letting them be part of the cultural heritage management.

Many Filipinos give more importance to the cultural practices where they find their true group identity and communal values. The values derived from their practices, which are translations of their knowledge and belief about Christmas as associated with festivities and spirituality, are believed to have been directly or indirectly influenced by the beliefs and practices brought by the tradition they later acquired. These Christian traditions are adapted in life based on judgment and decision. The community practices help people affirm their communal identity and thereby enrich their family values (Del Castillo, 2020).

This study sought to determine the Christmas practices known in Antequera, Bohol, and the cultural preservation mechanisms they have done on the practices. The questions focus on the known Christmas practices in Antequera, the challenges that keep the tradition going, its significance, and the mechanisms that support the identified Christmas practices. Some sub-questions involved the period when these practices were held; the music used and their movements, the participants and their roles, the preparation done by the community, and the values enhanced by the said practices. Furthermore, this study sought to rediscover the Christmas practices in Antequera and the initiative that the support mechanisms can take to overcome the community's challenges to keep those traditions going. The findings of the study would help them ensure sustainability in the implementation of culture and arts programs and activities that strengthen culture preservation, specifically the preservation of the identified Christmas practices.

METHODOLOGY

This study used a descriptive-qualitative research method. It is used to describe and understand the Christmas practices known and observed in Antequera, Bohol, specifically related to the following: *Igue-igue*, *Pastores*, and *Haring Herudes*, the support mechanism provided to safeguard and sustain these practices, and the challenges faced by the community in keeping the traditions going. A qualitative method was used to document the present status of their Christmas practices and to know what inspired the Antequeranons to continue and develop these traditions. The researchers chose Antequera, specifically barangay Angilan, because, in the past, they were known for doing these Christmas practices, and they were able to perform both in and out of Antequera through invitations. However, people seem to have forgotten it.

The participants of the study were the performers of the three Christmas practices, namely: *Igue-igue*, *Pastores*, *Haring Herudes*, and their respective choreographers. The researchers indicated that there were seven performers and three choreographers. Since three Christmas practices were being studied, the researchers decided to have one choreographer in each practice. *Igue-igue* and *Pastores* had two respondents, while *Haring Herudes* had three. To ensure the credibility of the participants, a criterion was set, such as performers of the practice, age, and knowledge about the practice. The age range was 50 to 70 years old. To check the performer's knowledge about the Christmas practices, the researchers asked them about their roles or part and their experiences while doing the said practice. The representatives of the Church and other institutions were selected according to their age (50-70), knowledge, and length of service (more than 40 years). The researchers respected the rights of the participants to participate in the study. They have the right to decline or withdraw from the study.

The researchers used guide questions for the LGU of Antequera, Bohol, particularly in Church and other institutions, in relation to the rediscovering of the traditional Christmas

practices in the town. [The study used the informal, structured, iterative interview.](#)

They followed the protocols and ethical considerations in research. There were two versions of this letter, English and Cebuano. They also asked for the participants' permission to record and take pictures of the interview for documentation purposes. There was no conflict of interest in this study. Their names and any other details were optional in the data collection for confidentiality and privacy purposes. All of the information collected was respected and trusted. They were given an informed consent form to sign as an agreement. All respondents were not forced to include all of the details requested by the researchers. They had the right to withdraw their participation during the study. The vulnerability of all the respondents was strictly prohibited from any publications for safety and privacy and to avoid risky circumstances. The researchers informed the respondents of whatever the findings would be.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

There were three Christmas practices identified: *Igue-igue*, *Haring Herudes*, and *Pastores Igue-igue* came from the act of rejecting others from entering the house, especially if they were poor. This practice is theater-like because it is a combination of singing and drama. In the first and second stanzas, Joseph and Mary, the singers, seek a place where they can rest after a long trip from Judea. In this scene, as they head towards their destination, they are knocking on random houses, asking for the owner's permission to let them in. Following this, the "*Igue-igue*," who acts as the homeowner, will ask Joseph and Mary to introduce themselves to assure that they are not thieves, especially since it is already late at night. Their response was in the form of singing. They introduce themselves as a poor couple and relative of the "*tig-igue*." However, they were declined because all their relatives were rich, and no one was named Joseph or Mary, who came from a low-income family. The performers who played Mary and Joseph will answer in a singing way, begging to allow them to stay even at the stairs on

that night. Unfortunately, the "igue-igue" did not agree to their plea; instead, he suggested they proceed to the manger.

This uncommon practice was done before the birth of Christ, as it shows the complicated journey of Mary and Joseph in searching for a house that will welcome them despite being strangers. It had a combination of singing and drama through *Igue*, in which the character acted as if he was angry as he drove Mary and Joseph away. Among the three Christmas practices, Igue-igue had the least number of members, and it only required a short time to practice. The participants practice days before the actual presentation, and they don't have any formal costumes unless it is for a competition. The costumes were not required unless it was a competition. The values enhanced in this Christmas practice were commitment and passion. It enhances commitment because to produce quality performance, the performers need to be committed to practicing. Also, keeping the tradition going requires commitment, especially in the face of unknown circumstances. If there is commitment, it automatically equates to passion. According to the performers, since they were children, they had already seen how passionate their father was doing the said Christmas practice they could adapt to growing up. It is not only for entertainment purposes, but it means more than that. It is a way of preserving a long Christmas tradition passed down from one generation to another.

"Haring Herodes" is based on the biblical story of the events surrounding the birth of Jesus, the Son of God, the Messiah. When Jesus Christ was born in the town of Bethlehem, Herod was the king in Jerusalem in search of the baby born to be the king of the Jews. A miracle scene is shown when Joseph and Mary, on their escape flight to safety, come across a shepherdess, "Bakera," sowing wheat. Still, as they walked past, the newly sown seeds sprouted, bore fruit, and ripened so that she was already harvesting wheat when the killer soldiers came and found the impossibility of finding the target couple and their child.

The script is composed of the lines of every character involved in the street play. The story culminates with a sword

fight between the brave shepherd mother, "Bakera," who vowed to save the baby boy but was vanquished, and her poor baby boy was beheaded by the Roman soldiers. This practice was the most awaited event during the Christmas season. The participants allocated one month for memorizing the lines and another month for the props making and their actual practice wherein the steps were taught. Regarding their costumes, the barangay only had the budget for the main character.

In contrast, the rest of the participants would be the ones to provide their costumes. It was unique because it was a combination of dancing, singing, drama, and the *komparsa*, which provided the overall music. Out of the three Christmas practices, Haring Herudes was the most intricate as it requires longer preparation both in practice and props-making. Every detail needed to be well-planned, and coordination was necessary between the performers and the musicians. In order to produce a quality performance, the barangay and the people who were part of Haring Herudes needed to allocate enough money and manpower. By performing and watching this Christmas practice, the enhanced values were solidarity, faith, and knowledge.

The researchers analyzed that having Haring Herudes made their culture colorful. The values enhanced in this Christmas tradition are creativity, patience, and solidarity. Creativity was evident in the way they told the story about this biblical event, which drew the attention of many people. Their joy in doing this practice is reflected in their eyes, which shows that they gave honor and pride to it. The tradition also enhances patience because of the long duration it takes to prepare the props, memorize the lines of the characters, and the actual practice. Also, the value of solidarity is strengthened with this tradition because the people of barangay Angilan were cooperative with the success of the performance. They willingly dedicate their time and effort to make it possible and memorable. The movements shown by the participants are only part of what she can remember in her performance.

Pastores are shepherds who went to Bethlehem with happiness to see the Son of Mary. These are joyful hymns with a

consistent message telling people to rejoice because the Savior was born. The shepherds' admiration is traditionally expressed by singing and dancing from one house to the next. It is frequently played by youngsters or teenagers in brightly colored clothes. The majority of them are female and wear lengthy skirts, puffed-sleeved round-necked shirts, and wide-brimmed hats. The *Pastores* sing about the shepherds who came to see the baby Jesus in the manger. The cheerful mood made dancing inevitable. Women wear caps with red ribbons and bring *castañuelas*. Their practice and costume preparation took two months to complete. Homeowners reward them with money, just as they do with traditional carolers.

It was amazing in the sense that it combined two movements, namely choral and theater, which made it more enjoyable for those watching it. Unlike Haring Herudes, its ways are not that time-consuming to prepare or practice. It also enhanced the value of Faith. Since *Pastores* is a part of the Nativity story, it further strengthens the faith of the people as Jesus Christ, who they believed to be the Savior, has come to the world to save the people from their sins. The faith of the youth is also strengthened because they were able to experience the tradition firsthand. The experience that they got from this can be an effective instrument to spread the faith.

Since the practices were based on the initiative of the people of *Barangay* Angilan, the Local Government Unit (LGU) of Antequera was not able to support it. Regarding funding, the LGU cannot give any assistance because there were no formal letters addressed to the municipal mayor or vice mayor. This is one of the reasons why the Christmas practices vanished; people from that time became unmotivated due to the limited budget of the barangay. Back then, the LGU knew about these Christmas practices because they were performed in and out of the municipality. Still, due to the lack of communication, they were not able to support them. According to the key informant, with the Church having its events during Christmas, the said three practices were not focused enough because of how hectic the schedule was during this time of the year. It was said that there was a preparation for the *Simbang Gabi* and a reenactment of the Nativity story. There was also a recreation of the Christmas

star descending from the sky and going to the manger where Christ was born. With this, the Church does not give attention to the barangay's Christmas practices because the Nativity summarizes the story of Igue-igue, Haring Herudes, and Pastores.

The performers cannot fully showcase the uniqueness and the values that people can get from the three Christmas practices because the Church did not emphasize them. According to the respondents, there were preparations for the Simbang Gabi as well as a reenactment of the Nativity story. The Christmas star was also reenacted, going from the sky to the manger where Jesus was born. The Church, therefore, overlooks the Barangay's Christmas practices since the Nativity summarizes Igue-igue, Haring Herudes, and Pastores.

According to the respondents, they did not receive any support from other institutions, such as schools and non-governmental organizations, because these Christmas practices were rooted in the barangay initiative. Just like the preceding two, the other institutions had nothing to do with it because, at that time, even if they were aware of these Christmas practices, they could not still intervene because it was all rooted in the initiative of the barangay. There were several reasons why these Christmas practices no longer exist. In terms of other institutions, there was a lack of coordination between them and the barangay.

According to an informant, the Christmas practices were not properly passed down to the younger generation because of the constant modernization, the death of the performers, and others forgetting how actually to do it. In addition, the costumes and some of the instruments were already gone and damaged because of time and other natural phenomena. Furthermore, there was a need for a bigger budget in order to produce a quality performance. Others may see it as mere Christmas practices, but in reality, it impacted the community, especially the people. In addition, they also had historical and cultural significance.

Three Christmas practices were identified in this study. Igue-igue is performed before Christmas. It is theater-like

because it has a combination of singing and drama through *Igue*, in which the character acts as if he is angry as he drives Mary and Joseph away. The participants of the said Christmas practice depend on who wants to join the practice or the performance itself. On the other hand, Haring Herudes is performed during and after Christmas. It is also theater-like because it has a combination of dancing, singing, drama, and the *komparsa*, which provide the overall music. Participants are the people of *Barangay Angilan*, especially the barangay officials.

In total, there were 21 members (16 performers and five *komparsa* members). Lastly, for Pastores, it is performed after Christmas until the celebration of the three kings. It is a combination of choral-like and theater-like movements because it is composed of singing while dancing to the music of the *komparsa*. There were 12 performers, all females, and five *Komparsa* members. Both the practices and the performers (Haring Herudes and Pastores) originated in Antequera.

In contrast, the performers of *Igue-igue* came from Dorol, Balilihan. Still, they became known for performing the Christmas practice in Antequera. Although the Christmas practices differ when it comes to their props and costumes, they have one thing in common: accompanying musicians. To perform well, enough time and manpower are required to prepare the materials or equipment. The significance of these practices was to celebrate Christmas and provide knowledge about what happened on the journey of the birth of Christ. It also served as entertainment during the Christmas season. These practices allowed the people to reminisce about the journey of His birth and the hardships that His parents went through.

The practices united people from different walks of life. It also strengthened their faith because of the lessons that they can get. The knowledge they gained from doing and watching the said practices enabled the spectators to share it with the younger ones.

The preparation for *Igue-igue* happens days before the actual performance. For Haring Herudes, the preparation is estimated for 2 months, and when it comes to making their props, they help each other. In Pastores, they spend an

estimated two months to prepare for the props, costumes, and practice. The values enhanced in Igue-igue and Haring Herudes are solidarity, faith, and knowledge. In *Pastores*, the values enhanced are rejoice, faith, solidarity, and knowledge.

For the support mechanism, the LGU of Antequera, the Church, and other institutions had nothing to do with it. These practices are the result of the initiative of the people of Barangay Angilan.

The Christmas practices were not present anymore due to the constant modernization, the death of the performers, and others forgetting how to do it. In addition, the costumes and some of the instruments were already gone and damaged because of time and other natural phenomena. There is also a need for a bigger budget to achieve a high-quality performance. The attention of the people is diverted, especially those in the Local Government Unit and the Church, so as a result, these practices were not given enough attention.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The people of Barangay Angilan, Antequera, and Bohol worked hard to sustain their Christmas traditions. It is just that it was not passed down to the younger generation because several reasons prevent them from doing so. People cannot fully understand the significance of these practices if they are not able to witness them from the start. Old practices do not automatically mean that they are obsolete already. Young folks can still enjoy it as it has values and wisdom that can be imparted to them. That is why the preservation of these social practices is important so that future generations will still be able to see it and feel a sense of pride in what it is like to have a rich culture.

The LGU, specifically the Council for Culture and Arts, shall strengthen and ensure the sustainability and implementation of cultural arts programs that promote cultural preservation, such as Christmas practices. In order to continuously promote the culture, the people of the community may interact and help LGU to safeguard and preserve their

practices. Non-government organizations such as schools and churches that advocate for culture preservation can actively participate and collaborate with the Local Government Unit and the community.

REFERENCES

- Alivizatou-Barakou, M., et al. (n.d.). *Intangible cultural heritage and new technologies: Challenges and opportunities for cultural preservation and development*.
- Antequera Bohol Philippines Guide. (n.d.). *Bohol-Philippines.com*. Retrieved March 22, 2021, from <https://www.bohol-philippines.com/antequera.html>
- Antequera, Bohol. (2018). *Bohol-Philippines.com*. <https://www.bohol-philippines.com/antequera.html>
- Anunciado, M. et al. (2019). *Haring Herodes: A monograph in oral traditions and expressions*. Holy Name University.
- Bernardo, A. B. I., et al. (1998). *Understanding behavior: Bridging cultures*.
- Bonn, M., et al. (2016). Preserving intangible heritage: Defining a research agenda.
- Carbayas, R. J., & Del Castillo, M. R. (2020). *Christmas in the Philippines: Beyond popular religious tradition* (2nd ed.). https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341726916_Christmas_in_the_Philippines_Beyond_Popular_Religious_Tradition
- Cultural heritage care and management. (n.d.). *Google Books*. <https://books.google.com.ph/books?v=onepage&q&f=true>
- Cultural identity theory. (2014, September 8). *Communication Theory*. <https://www.communicationtheory.org/cultural-identity-theory/>
- Dumaraos, G. (2017, August 30). 11 things you should know about Filipino culture. *Culture Trip*. <https://theculturetrip.com/asia/philippines/articles/11-things-you-should-know-about-the-filipino-culture/>

- Evolutionary theories: Social change. (n.d.). *Sociology Guide*. <https://www.sociologyguide.com/social-change/evolutionary-theories.php>
- Fajutag, J. (2020, November 10). The Philippines: Culture and tradition. *Globalization Partners International*. <https://www.globalizationpartners.com/2015/02/20/the-philippines-culture-and-tradition/>
- Ioannides, M., et al. (Eds.). (2017). Mixed reality and gamification for cultural heritage (pp. 129–158). *Springer International Publishing*. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-49607-8_5
- Jokilehto, J. (n.d.). *Preservation theory unfolding*. <http://orcp.hustoj.com/wp-content/uploads/2016/01/2006-Preservation-Theory-Unfolding.pdf>
- UNESCO. (2020, November 20). *UNESCO prizes*. <https://en.unesco.org/prizes#CLT>
- Philippines – History and culture. (n.d.). *IExplore*. <https://www.iexplore.com/articles/travel-guides/south-and-southeast-asia/philippines/history-and-culture>
- Rahman, F., & Letlora, P. S. (2018). Cultural preservation: Rediscovering the endangered oral tradition of Maluku (A case study on "Kapata" of Central Maluku). *ERIC*. <https://eric.ed.gov>
- Reading: Theoretical perspectives on culture. (n.d.). *Lumen*. <https://courses.lumenlearning.com/alamo-sociology/chapter/reading-theoretical-perspectives-on-culture/>
- Resabal, C. (2017, December 21). Folk society's Christmas musical tradition dying in Bohol. *VERA Files*. <https://verafiles.org/articles/folk-societys-christmasmusical-tradition-dying-bohol>
- Resabal, C. (2017, November 7). Cultural hubs showcasing Bohol heritage boost tourism and livelihood. *VERA Files*. <https://verafiles.org/articles/cultural-hubs-showcasing-bohol-heritage-boost-tourism-and-livelihood>

- Sarmiento, J. (2018). *Initiatives for the preservation and protection of the cultural heritage of Tanday, Corella, Bohol*. Holy Name University.
- The Manila Times. (2015, December 26). 'Daygon' tradition fast disappearing. <https://www.manilatimes.net/2015/12/26/todays-headline-photos/regions/daygon-tradition-fast-disappearing/236405>
- Tirol, A. (2008). Enacting the Bohol arts and cultural heritage code (Page 2). *BACH Code*. https://bohol.gov.ph/downloads/BACH-CODE-Final_Ord2008-002-27febo8.pdf
- Torres, M. V., et al. (2019). *The cultural programs and activities of selected LGUs in Bohol: Problems and challenges*. Holy Name University.
- Trip, C. (n.d.). About us. *Culture Trip*. <https://theculturetrip.com/about-us>

